

A study on dog bite patients and their management attending health care facilities in Amalapuram, Dr.B.R.Ambedkar Konaseema District Andhra Pradesh

FIRST AUTHOR: Dr. Kotha Prasanna, Assistant Professor, Department of community medicine, Konaseema Institute of Medical Sciences & Research Foundation, Amalapuram, Andhra Pradesh.

SECOND AUTHOR & CORRESPONDING AUTHOR: Dr. Renu Vasant Sulakhe, HOD & Professor, Department of community.

THIRD AUTHOR: Dr. D. Bhavana Ramyasri, PG, Department of community medicine, Konaseema Institute of Medical Sciences & Research Foundation, Amalapuram, Andhra Pradesh.

Background: Rabies is a fatal zoonotic disease primarily transmitted through dog bites, posing a significant public health threat, particularly in regions with large stray dog populations. This study aim to assess the severity, and factors associated with dog bite injuries, as well as their management, in Amalapuram.

Methodology: A hospital-based prospective study was conducted among individuals (1–80 years) attending OPD services with dog bite injuries. Data were collected using face-to-face interviews with a semi-structured questionnaire. Statistical analysis was performed using IBM SPSS software (version 20).

Results: The study included 148 participants, with a mean age of 35.05 years (± 20 SD). Males (59.5%) were more affected than females (40.5%). Stray dogs accounted for 60.1% of cases, and pet dogs for 39.9%. The most common category of injuries was Category-II (54.1%), followed by Category-III (32.4%) and Category-I (13.5%). Most participants (86.5%) administered first aid at home, and 94.6% completed their vaccination schedules. The study found significant associations between the nature of the dog and activity at the time of the incident ($p=0.000$), site of injury ($p=0.000$), and location of the bite ($p=0.000$). However, the severity of injury ($p=0.088$) did not show statistical significance. Immunoglobulin was administered in 32.4% of cases, with a significant correlation between site of injury and immunoglobulin administration ($p=0.003$).

Conclusion: The study highlights the burden of dog bite injuries, with stray dogs being the primary contributors. The predominance of lower limb injuries and high treatment-seeking behaviour indicate the need for continued awareness and control measures. Strengthening rabies prevention strategies, improving public awareness, and implementing stray dog control programs are essential to reduce rabies-related morbidity and mortality.

Key words: Dog bites, Public health, Immunoglobulin therapy

Introduction

Rabies is primarily a zoonotic disease of warm-blooded animals particularly carnivorous such as dogs, jackals & wolves caused by Lyssavirus type 1. ¹Rabies” word is derived from the Latin word “*rabere*,” which means to be mad, to rage, or to rave.² Rabies is estimated to cause 59 000 human deaths annually in over 150 countries, with 95% of cases occurring in Africa and Asia. Due to underreporting and uncertain estimates, this number is likely a gross underestimate. The burden of disease is disproportionately borne by rural poor populations, with approximately half of cases attributable to children under 15 years of age.³

Rabies has 100% fatality, once clinical symptoms appear.⁴ Infected saliva of a rabid animal through a bite is the predominant mode of rabies virus entry in the human. The consequences of the introduction of rabies virus are determined by a number of factors like location of the wound, severity of the wound, amount of virus inoculated, and current and previous status of immunization.⁵

Rationale:- Dog bites are a significant public health issue, primary cause of rabies transmission to humans especially in areas with large stray dog populations understanding the incidence and severity in amalapuram can help in assessing the local public health burden.

Category	Injury
Category -I	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Touching or feeding of animals • Licks on intact skin
Category -II	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Nibbing of uncovered skin • Minor scratches or abrasions without bleeding
Category -III	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Single or multiple transdermal bites or scratches • Licks on broken skin • Contamination of mucous membrane with saliva

MATERIALS AND METHODS

- **STUDY DESIGN:** This is a hospital based, prospective study.
- **STUDY PARTICIPANTS:** People of all age groups (1–80 years) who attended OPD services with a history of dog bite injuries.
- **STUDY SETTING:** OPD of AH Amalapuram, OPD of CHC Razole, OPD of PHC Bandarulanka, OPD of CHC P.Gannavaram.
- **SAMPLE TECHNIQUES:** Convenient sampling
- **INCLUSION CRITERIA:** Patients of all age groups who attended OPD services of healthcare facilities with a history of dog bite injuries near Amalapuram.
- **EXCLUSION CRITERIA:**
 1. Patients who were not willing to give consent.
 2. Patients who were not able to communicate were excluded.
- **DATA COLLECTION PROCEDURE:** After obtaining informed consent from the patients, data was collected through face-to-face interviews using a pre-designed, semi-structured questionnaire. Follow-up of patients for vaccination was conducted over 3 months.
- **CONFIDENTIALITY:** Particulars and details of all the participants were kept confidential throughout the study; only summary of the details was used for declaring the result
- **ETHICAL CONSIDERATION:** Institutional ethics committee approval was taken and informed consent was obtained.
- **DATA ANALYSIS AND INTERPRETATION:** Data was entered using Microsoft Excel sheet. Summarisation and analysis of data was carried out by using IBM SPSS Software version 20(licensed). Descriptive Statistics: Mean, Percentage and Standard Deviation.

Results

Table: 1 Demographic details of study participants

Parameters	Frequency	Percentage (%)
AGE		
1-10 Years	20	13.5
11-20 Years	24	16.2
21-40 Years	47	31.8
>40 Years	57	38.5
SEX		
Male	88	59.5
Female	60	40.5
NATURE OF DOG		
Stray dog	89	60.1
Pet dog	59	39.9
CATEGORY OF DOG BITE INJURY		
Category-I	20	13.5
Category-II	80	54.1
Category-III	48	32.4
First aid given at home immediately after dog bite		
Yes	128	86.5
No	20	13.5

The mean age of study participants is 35.05 years (± 20 SD). The majority 57 (38.5%) are above 40 years old, with a nearly equal distribution across other age groups. And had a higher proportion of males (59.5%) compared to females (40.5%). Most dog bites were caused by stray dogs 89 (60.1%), while pet dogs accounted for 39.9%. Category-II injuries 80

(54.1%) were the most common, followed by Category-III (32.4%) and Category-I (13.5%). The most of participants (86.5%) administered first aid at home immediately after the dog bite, while 13.5% did not.

Table 2. Association between Nature of dog and activity at the time of incident

Nature of Dog	ACTIVITY AT THE TIME OF INCIDENT			Total	chi-square	p-value
	while walking on street	while playing	others			
Stray dog	74(83.1%)	12(13.5%)	3(3.4%)	89(100%)	55.33	0.000
Pet dog	13(22%)	41(69.5%)	5(8.5%)	59(100%)		
Total	87(58.8%)	53(35.8%)	8(5.4%)	148(100%)		

Stray dogs were more likely to be involved in incidents while walking on the street (83.1%), whereas pet dogs were more frequently involved while playing (69.5%). Which shows a significant association between the nature of the dog and the activity at the time of the incident ($\chi^2 = 55.33$, $p = 0.000$).

Table 3. Association between nature of dog and site of injury

Nature of Dog	SITE OF INJURY			Total	chi-square	p-value
	Face/head neck	Upper body/limbs	Lower body /limbs			
Stray dog	2(2.2%)	17(19.1%)	70(78.7%)	89(100%)	18.649	0.000
Pet dog	4(6.8%)	29(49.2%)	26(44.1%)	59(100%)		
Total	6(4.1%)	46(31.1%)	96(64.9%)	148(100%)		

Among stray dog bites, the majority (78.7%) occurred on the lower body/limbs, while only 2.2% affected the face/head/neck. In contrast, pet dog bites were more evenly distributed, with 49.2% affecting the upper body/limbs and 44.1% on the lower body/limbs. The chi-square value (18.649) and the p-value (0.000) indicate a statistically significant association between the nature of the dog and the site of injury.

Table 4. Association between nature of dog and location of dog bite incident

Nature of Dog	LOCATION OF DOG BITE INCIDENT			Total	chi-square	p-value
	At home	At street	At work place			
Stray dog	11(12.4%)	72(80.9%)	6(6.7%)	89(100%)	93.955	0.000
Pet dog	55(93.2%)	4(6.8%)	0(0.0%)	59(100%)		
Total	66(44.6%)	76(51.4%)	6(4.1%)	148(100%)		

The majority of bites caused by stray dogs (80.9%) occurred on the street, while most bites from pet dogs (93.2%) happened at home. Very few cases were reported at the workplace. The chi-square test value (93.955) and the p-value (0.000) indicate a statistically significant association between the nature of the dog and the location of the bite, suggesting that stray dogs are more likely to bite in public areas, whereas pet dog bites occur predominantly at home.

Table 5. Association between nature of dog and category of dog bite injury

Nature of Dog	CATEGORY OF DOG BITE INJURY			Total	chi-square	p-value
	Category-I	Category-II	Category-III			
Stray dog	11(12.4%)	43(48.3%)	35(39.3%)	89(100%)	4.997	0.088
Pet dog	9(15.3%)	37(62.7%)	13(22%)	59(1009%)		
Total	20(13.5%)	80(54.1%)	48(32.4%)	148(100%)		

Among stray dog bite cases, 12.4% were Category-I, 48.3% were Category-II, and 39.3% were Category-III. For pet dog bites, 15.3% fell under Category-I, 62.7% under Category-II, and 22% under Category-III. The chi-square value of 4.997 and a p-value of 0.088 suggest that the association between the nature of the dog and the severity of the bite is not statistically significant.

Figure:1 Showing Vaccination response rate

The pie chart shows that the vaccination response rate is **94.60%**, indicating that these individuals have completed their vaccinations appropriate to their child's age, while **5.40%** have incomplete vaccinations. The reasons for this **5.40%** not completing their vaccinations include negligence and the intention to continue the vaccination process at another hospital.

Table 6. Association between site of injury and immunoglobulin given to patients

Site of injury	Immunoglobulin given to patient		Total	chi-square	p-value
	Yes	No			
Face/head neck	2(1.4%)	4(2.7%)	6(4.1%)	11.629	0.003
Upper body/limbs	6(4.1%)	40(27.0%)	59(39.9%)		
Lower body/limbs	40(27.0%)	56(37.8%)	46(31.1%)		
Total	48(32.4%)	100(67.6%)	148(100%)		

Among the 148 patients, 32.4% received immunoglobulin, while 67.6% did not. The highest proportion of immunoglobulin administration was observed in lower body/limb injuries (27.0%), followed by upper body/limbs (4.1%) and face/head/neck (1.4%). The association between the site of injury and the administration of immunoglobulin to patients showed statistically significant with a p-value of 0.003.

DISCUSSION

In the present study, the incidence of dog bite injuries was observed at an average rate of 12 cases per week, which is significantly higher than the study conducted by Dr. Joshua Briotti et al.⁷, where the average was only 4 cases per week. This suggests a greater prevalence of dog bite incidents in the current study setting. The median age of victims in the present study was 35 years (IQR: 36, range 1–80 years), while Briotti's study reported a slightly younger median age of 32 years (IQR: 32, range 1–97 years). This indicates that dog bite injuries affect individuals across all age groups, with a slightly higher median age in the present study.

Regarding the location of dog bite incidents, the majority of cases in the present study occurred on the street (51.45%), followed by at home (44.6%). This is comparable to Uzma Rahim Khan et al.⁶'s study, where most dog bite injuries occurred outside the house (94.2%) and were caused by stray dogs. However, in contrast to Khan's findings, where most incidents were unprovoked, the present study observed that a significant proportion of bites occurred due to specific activities, including crossing near a dog (50%) and playing near dogs (31.1%), with 11.5% of incidents being provoked.

The site of injury predominantly involved the lower limbs (64.9%), followed by the upper limbs (31.1%). This is consistent with the findings of both Khan et al. and Briotti et al., where lower limbs were the most frequently affected site (79.8% and 74%, respectively). The predominance of lower limb injuries aligns with the common behaviour of dogs targeting the legs when reacting defensively or aggressively.^{6,7}

In terms of treatment-seeking behaviour, 87.8% of the participants in the present study sought medical care on the same day, which is similar to Khan et al.'s study, where 87.7% of patients presented promptly for treatment. However, Briotti et al.⁷ reported a lower rate of immediate treatment-seeking (67%). This suggests that awareness regarding the urgency of post-exposure prophylaxis may be higher in certain populations, possibly due to differences in healthcare access or public health campaigns.

Conclusion

The study highlights the significant public health burden of dog bite injuries, particularly from stray dogs, with most incidents occurring on streets. The findings emphasize the need for improved awareness, timely medical intervention, and enhanced rabies prevention strategies. Despite a high vaccination response rate (94.6%), gaps remain in immunoglobulin administration and treatment adherence. The study underscores the importance of public health initiatives, stray dog management, and community education to mitigate the risk of rabies and improve post-exposure care.

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